

Customer Satisfaction towards Online Shopping

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ABSTRACT: Online shopping is the biggest part of customer attraction as well as customer satisfaction. In today's technology environment, most businesses rely on internet purchasing to both please their consumers and attract new ones. The effects of online shopping on improving customer satisfaction are the subject of this study report. The study also sought to determine the effects of online shopping on improving customer satisfaction in retail establishments. The research tasks entailed an ethical construction of a questionnaire keeping in view the research topic and tasks at hand. The construction of the survey was done keeping multiple touch points in consideration. Extensive research was done to identify the most prominent issues in the realm of online shopping. The survey was constructed based on these observations and was then circulated to a group of 100 respondents of varying ages, genders, and from different physical locations. Likert scales were used to gather experience-based data from all respondents. After being working on the research, we have come to learn that customer satisfaction plays a vital role in how the choices of people to shop online. Websites offering online shopping must have good customer services and user-friendly applications or websites to be easily accessible to the public and therefore making them prefer online shopping over in-person shopping. The study also revealed that online shopping has a variety of consequences (age and gender) and according to the analysis, online shopping assists in good quality, access, and comfort, resulting in increased customer satisfaction.

KEYWORDS: Attitude, Customer Behavior, Customer Satisfaction, Online shopping.

INTRODUCTION

Keeping in mind the technological advancements brought about in the world, many day-to-day chores have been shifted to the internet. The most important shift to the internet is online shopping. It is not only convenient to shop from the comfort of your home but it is also time-efficient and prevents unnecessary stress people experience while shopping [1]. This research helps to highlight customer satisfaction ensured to make online shopping a good experience. Although online shopping seems like a better hassle-free option, it is important to take certain measures to optimize customer satisfaction. Important measures to take whilst considering customer satisfaction include quality information, being user-friendly, easy modes of transactions, up-to-the-mark delivery services, and a good helpline [2]. It is important to understand the needs of the customers while shopping online to better the system up a hand. This research highlighted the different ways in which customer satisfaction can be achieved and what measure affects it.

The statement of the problem that caused this research to occur was: "How does customer satisfaction affect online shopping?" The primary question was accompanied by numerous subsidiary questions concerning the importance of customer satisfaction, the correlation of online shopping and customer satisfaction, and different practices that affect customer satisfaction. The research also touches upon some of the reasons why people prefer shopping online, which help to cater to the question of how customer satisfaction can be improved keeping in mind the needs of the customers? By the completion of the research, the reader was able to answer the above-mentioned questions with a comprehensive knowledge of each aspect which helped improve the online shopping experience. Moreover, it provided an overview of the future where everything is suspected to be carried out virtually [3]. The objective of this research is to overview the Customer response towards Online Shopping. This research highlights the effects of customer satisfaction on online shopping. It also provides a comprehensive overview of how online shopping can be made a better experience by putting forth the underlying correlation of customer satisfaction in boosting the number of people who shop online. This research was a help to identify different aspects of online shopping which can be improved along with giving a contrast of how various policies end up having dual effects.

By this research, we aim to provide a comprehensive overview of how online shopping can be made a better experience by putting forth the underlying correlation of customer satisfaction in boosting the number of people who shop online. This research was a help

to identify different aspects of online shopping which can be improved along with giving a contrast of how various policies end up having dual effects. The research has weighed the scope of different practices and their utility to increase customer satisfaction. Although the research was informative and a building block in understanding how online shopping can be improved, it does have limitations like a constraint sample size and the time frame in which the research is taking place. The pandemic does not allow us to meet people in person to get their unfiltered opinions. Moreover, customer satisfaction can be narrowed down to personal likes and dislikes making it subjective and therefore harder to work with. However, we have taken precautionary measures to minimize the drawbacks like including a variety of people surveyed.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

A research hypothesis is a statement of expectation or prediction that was being tested by research. A research hypothesis is a specific, clear, and testable proposition or predictive statement about the possible outcome of a scientific research study based on a particular property of a population, such as presumed differences between groups on a particular variable or relationships between variables. Specifying the research hypotheses is one of the most important steps in planning a scientific quantitative research study. A quantitative researcher usually states an a priori expectation about the results of the study in one or more research hypotheses before conducting the study, because the design of the research study and the planned research design often is determined by the stated hypotheses. In your hypothesis, you are predicting the relationship between variables. Through the disciplinary insights gained in the research process throughout the year, you “prove” your hypothesis.

There are two types, namely, null hypothesis and alternative hypothesis. Research generally starts with a problem. Next, these hypotheses provide the researcher with some specific restatements and clarifications of the research problem. Keeping in mind our primary question, we work to highlight the effects of customer satisfaction on online shopping. We expect that increased customer satisfaction increases the number of users who shop online. It is expected that improved customer satisfaction resulted in easy access to the online shops making it more convenient for the user. It is therefore expected that customer satisfaction has a direct positive relationship with online shopping. For analyzing the primary data collected for this report, several hypotheses have been developed. H1: There is a difference in mean on online shopping based on customer satisfaction, product quality, and comfort/ease of access. H2: There is a difference in the mean of online shopping based on Gender. H3: There is a difference in the mean of online shopping based on age

LITERATURE REVIEW

Online shopping is recent even more important than it used to be due to the pandemic which has effectively halted many conventional forms of shopping that we are used to. This makes it important to study the factors that impact customer satisfaction in an online setting to understand customer behavior and to optimize our services to best suit our customers' needs. Research on online shopping customer satisfaction suggests that information quality, merchandise attributes, how capable they are of managing their transactions, the security and privacy the service offer the customers, the website design, customer service, and the delivery are very strong indicators of customer satisfaction in the setting of online shopping. Research has also found the impact of response time to not be significantly linked to customer satisfaction [2].

Many scholars and literary discussions have surrounded the online medium of shopping to understand the process that is moving more and more customers into the realm of online shopping. Some scholars have used the technological boom to advocate for this recent phenomenon while some have advocated for aggressive marketing campaigns as the reason. Davis [4] conducted early research in which he tried to understand this process in its holistic sense. He found two main reasons i.e. enjoyment of consumers and their relative ease as compared to the traditional shopping process. This can help explain the modern shopping trend to this day because these factors are still relevant and can explain the thought process of consumers when they go online and shop for different things.

While this gives us a standard definition to understand the process, but a deep understanding needs to be developed to understand the problems of online shopping to understand the plight and benefits of this system. Tandon [5] published research in which they identified different problems that have affected consumers in this business model. One of the pertinent causes that have affected the consumers is the massive range of products that is available on the database. This makes it difficult for customers to give complete attention to online activity.

Another research has identified reliability of the product or services the customer is purchasing, the delivery performance of the service used for delivery of the product, the website design of the product, and the variety of products that are available to the customers are the four most important factors that influence customers' satisfaction with the practice of online shopping. This research also found no important relationship exists between the time saved during this process and the satisfaction of customers with the practice of online shopping [6]. Very important research concludes that the reason people are inclined towards online shopping is its appeal because of convenience and this convenience entails or in other words can be defined and described by elements such as saving time through this method, avoiding the insufferable stress caused by in-person shopping, the abundance of options and information on the products they are purchasing, the ease of access to these services, the user-friendly nature of websites, flexible timings for ordering and being less costly [7]. However, the drawback to this method of shopping is the safety and privacy concerns that cause significant worry to the customers. In addition to these unclear policies on product warranties and unclear return and exchange policies, lack or absence of personalized customer care which used to make customers feel valued, etc. are some of the barriers that are in the way of online shopping being embraced by everyone [8]. In addition to this, changes to online shopping recommended by researchers include security and privacy issues and making it as trustworthy as possible [8].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND RESEARCH PLAN

Data and the utilization of data in research are essential components of any good research plan. To logically analyze data and to take a plan-based approach to solve various research questions, people utilize the strategy of "research design", which helps them define a plan and a step-by-step approach to understanding a research question by collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data. The research population, we were abiding by while carrying out this research encompassed both quantitative and qualitative study. We plan on using interviews and surveys as our primary sources of information and journals, articles and books as our secondary sources of information. For the quantitative part of the research, we were taken into consideration data compiled from surveys conducted amongst the public. We were considering a sample size of 100 respondents and the survey was conducted via google forms. We are not targeting a certain type of population rather we are considering a variety of people including housewives, working parents, teenagers, and the elderly. This was helping us to get a broad overview of how customer satisfaction varies from person to person. The interviews that were conducted would be held through zoom meetings, keeping in mind the current situation of the pandemic.

Research instruments, also commonly known as data-collection instruments are tools used to collect data that can aid in the progression of a particular research task. There are several popular research instruments used for data collection, such as online forms, surveys, interviews, and forums. For instrument quality, it is essential to incorporate ethical practices in the research and data collection processes. Researchers, for instance, must make sure that the identity and privacy of online respondents are protected unless the respondents consent to their identities being revealed. Data collection must be done with integrity and unethical practices such as data theft or plagiarizing data collected by other research modules must be avoided.

DATA ANALYSIS

The results and findings indicate that most respondents feel that customer satisfaction has a very strong link with the increase in online shopping and that a lack of customer satisfaction can be potentially damaging. Results by data analysis presented that 58% of the population in questionnaire shows satisfaction in the sale of the product, product quality was marked by 23%, comfort/ease of access by 10% while other 9% of questionnaire as shown in figure 1. A significant proportion of both younger and older people view online shopping as a powerful force and a convenient option, although this feeling is much stronger within the younger population as compared to the older population as shown in Figures 2 and 3.

Figure 1. Representation of major issues in online shopping questionnaire

Figure 2. Percentage of Gender representation in online shopping questionnaire

Figure 3. Age group representation in online shopping questionnaire

CONCLUSION

The research tasks entailed an ethical construction of a questionnaire keeping in view the research topic and tasks at hand. The

construction of the survey was done keeping multiple touchpoints in consideration. Extensive research was done to identify the most prominent issues in the realm of online shopping. The survey was constructed based on these observations and was then circulated to a group of 100 respondents of varying ages, genders, and from different physical locations. Likert scales were used to gather experience-based data from all respondents. The entire process was kept highly ethical, with anonymity and the consent of all participants involved completely preserved. After being working on the research, we have come to learn that customer satisfaction plays a vital role in how the choices of people to shop online. Websites offering online shopping must have good customer services and user-friendly applications or websites to be easily accessible to the public and therefore making them prefer online shopping over in-person shopping.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made to promote awareness in online shopping: Problems encountered by purchasers during online shopping, such as delivery delays, broken items, or any other trust concerns, should be rectified to turn them into regular online consumers. To reach the greatest number of clients, the purchasing procedure must also be user-friendly. Because the statistics show that most customers prefer online shopping to conventional shopping, large and effective ads the accessibility, product quality, and other positive qualities should be made to stimulate client interest. It might be an excellent marketing strategy to encourage consumers who purchase online to promote it to others. According to the results of our study, the sensation of becoming overcharged might be a factor in people not suggesting online shopping to others. As a result, pricing and commodity quality should continue to complement one another to encourage consumer participation. As a result, through establishing a better brand quality reputation, as well as addressing consumer issues throughout product delivery, Customers can be happy and loyal to a business that provides online services.

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